

GENDER AND LANGUAGE: DIFFERENCES AND SIMILARITIES IN WOMEN'S AND MEN'S SPEECH

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Annotatsiya: Ayollar va erkaklar nutqidagi soʻzlar va muloqot madaniyati oʻziga xos xususiyatga ega boʻlib, ular nafaqat lugʻat boyligi, balki gaplarning tuzilishida hamda intonatsiyasida ham bir-biridan sezilarli darajada farq qiladi va ularning birliklari matnlarda turlicha ishlatiladi. Ular nutqining shu kabi farqli jihatlari borasida tilshunoslikda bir qancha ishlar amalga oshirilgan boʻlib, baʼzi xalqlarda ayollar nutqi alohida bir tadqiqot sifatida jamiyatga kirib kelgan. Shu bilan bir qatorda, jamiyatda chuqur ildiz otgan gender stereotiplari ham mavjud boʻlgan, oʻzgartirish lozim boʻlgan tushunchadir. Bugungi kunda ushbu tushunchalarni yangicha lingvistik nuqtayi nazardan qarab qayta koʻrib chiqish va bir nechta zamonaviy qisman yoki butunlay oʻzgarishlarga mos ravishda talqin qilish kerak boʻlgan dolzarb vazifadir. Ushbu maqolada ayol va erkak nutqidagi gender tenglikning mohiyati, tilshunoslikdagi oʻrni va rivojlanish tarixi batafsil yoritiladi. Shunigdek, gender tafovutlarining ijtimoiy, madaniy va eng asosiysi diniy omillari bilan ham bogʻliqligi tushuntiriladi va shu bilan birga ayol va erkak nutqidagi leksik, fonetik, Grammatik va asosiysi pragmatik farqlar til materiallari (oʻzbek, rus, ingliz va boshqa tillar) misolida koʻrsatiladi.

Kalit soʻzlar: pragmatik, madaniy, diniy, stereotip, lingvistika, tilshunoslik, evfemiya hodisasi.

Аннотация: Слова и культура общения в речи женщин и мужчин обладают своеобразными особенностями, различаясь не только богатством словарного запаса, но и структурой предложений, а также интонацией, вследствие чего их языковые единицы по-разному используются в текстах. В языкознании было проведено множество исследований, посвящённых подобным различиям мужской и женской речи, а в некоторых культурах женская речь стала самостоятельным объектом научного изучения. Наряду с этим в обществе существуют глубоко укоренившиеся гендерные стереотипы, которые требуют переосмысления и изменения. На сегодняшний день актуальной задачей является рассмотрение данных понятий с новой лингвистической точки зрения и их интерпретация в соответствии с современными частичными или полными социальными изменениями. В данной статье подробно освещаются сущность гендерного равенства в мужской и женской речи, его место в языкознании и история развития. Также объясняется связь гендерных различий с социальными, культурными и, прежде всего, религиозными факторами. Кроме того, лексические, фонетические, грамматические и, главным образом, прагматические различия в речи женщин и мужчин демонстрируются на примерах языковых материалов узбекского, русского, английского и других языков

Ключевые слова: прагматический, культурный, религиозный, стереотип, лингвистика, языкознание, явление эвфемии.

Annotation: The words and communication culture in women's and men's speech possess distinctive characteristics, differing significantly not only in vocabulary richness, but also in sentence structure and intonation, while their linguistic units are used differently in texts. In linguistics, numerous studies have been conducted on such distinctive aspects of male and female speech, and in some cultures women's speech has emerged as a separate field of research. At the same time, gender stereotypes deeply rooted in society remain concepts that require reconsideration and transformation. Today, it is an urgent task to review these notions from a new linguistic perspective and interpret them in accordance with modern partial or complete social changes. This article thoroughly examines the essence of gender equality in women's and men's speech, its place in linguistics, and the history of its development. Furthermore, the article explains the connection of gender differences with social, cultural, and especially religious factors, while lexical, phonetic, grammatical, and most importantly pragmatic differences in male and female speech are illustrated through language materials from Uzbek, Russian, English, and other languages.

Keywords: pragmatic, cultural, religious, stereotype, linguistics, philology, euphemism phenomenon.

INTRODUCTION

Today, gender studies not only address equality but also examine politics and the differences between women's and men's speech. Lexical differences in linguistics based on gender are also explained through the psychology of speech. What is gender? How is it related to language? And what is language itself? Questions like these are addressed by the fields of sociolinguistics and linguistics (Bondaletov, 1987).

Gender is a concept that represents equality between women and men and defines their roles in society. Today, it has become one of the most widely discussed topics, giving rise to numerous debates. In simple terms, we call it 'gender', but in reality, it carries deeper, complex meanings connected to social and even political contexts. This concept is not related to biological sex, rather, it is a social construct. Biological sex is innate, whereas gender defines an individual's social role within society. Language, in turn, serves as a reflection of these roles.

METHODS

Gender is expressed through language. It becomes clearly visible in aspects such as word choice, sentence structure, communication style, intonation, and tone. For example, expressions like 'she gossips a lot' in English are often used in reference to women, which reflects how gender stereotypes are transferred into language and normalized in everyday usage.

The relationship between gender and language is a broad and significant concept. The first studies and research on this connection emerged in the 1970s (Lakoff, 1975). In her work "Language and Woman's place" (1975), Robin Lakoff demonstrates that features of women's speech- such as softer expressions, hedging, and polite forms- are closely related to their social status in society (Lakoff, 1975).

The connection with sociolinguistics and linguistics lies in the fact that these fields examine such phenomena. They study how men and women differ in tone, style, and patterns of communication. According to gender and linguistic research, differences in men's and women's speech are influenced by social roles, cultural context, and communicative purposes (Bondaletov, 1987). Women tend to use more expressive and

cooperative language, often emphasizing politeness, whereas men's speech is more direct and focused on conveying information. As a result, men's speech may sometimes appear more abrupt, while women's speech often involves the use of euphemism (Ohunova, 2025).

RESULTS

The phenomenon of euphemism is the use of, milder, softer expressions to replace words that are considered rude, harsh, or negative in meaning when speaking or conveying information. Below are some examples of euphemism:

Words:	Soft equivalent:
Sick/ill	Not feeling very well
Rich	Financially well-off
Alone	With limited family support
Anxiety	A bit upset
Spicy	Slightly sharp in taste
Good/ well	Having high spiritual
Small	Slightly smaller in size
Died	Passed away
Poor	Not financially well-of
Old	Elderly

From a linguistic perspective, we can observe several differences and variations in the speech of men and women. One of the key distinctions lies in phonetic features. Women's speech is often characterized by a softer and lower tone, whereas men's speech tends to be louder and as I said above sometimes heavier in tone.

In addition, men often use more abstract nouns in their speech. It is also noted that men tend to use more active voice verbs, and their speech contains more interrogative and negative sentences compared of that of women (Ohunova, 2025). Furthermore, it should be emphasized that women generally use more words to express their thoughts than men and often seek confirmation or agreement in conversation.

It is also important to note that, in some contexts, gender dynamics may portray women as more dominant in communication.

From the religious perspectives again, it is often emphasized that women should show respect and modesty in their behavior towards men, including speaking in a polite and moderate tone and maintaining a sense of humility (Tong, 2009). In uzbek culture, such norms are considered important social values.

DISCUSSION

At the same time, Islam highlights the importance of respecting, protecting, and valuing women to demonstrate modesty and respectful conduct in their interactions with men (Tong, 2009).

In the issue of gender and language, differences in speech between the two genders are widely discussed in society; however, similarities should not be overlooked. These similarities are mainly reflected in the following aspects:

- Language system: both women and men follow the same linguistic rules. For example, sentence structure in the Uzbek language is the same for both;
- Communicative purposes: both express opinions, show empathy, convey information, and establish social connections with others;

•Use of communicative tools: both men and women ask questions, respond, and provide explanations.

Such similarities may not always be noticeable in society, but they become more apparent in group interactions.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that speech style depends more on upbringing, environment, and culture than on gender. Therefore, despite certain differences, men and women share many common features in their speech. Gender equality is not only a widely discussed issue in foreign countries but is also gaining importance in Uzbek society. This indicates that the social status of Uzbek women is gradually increasing, and their rights and roles- both legally and religiously- are becoming more equal to those of men. However, it is important to maintain humility and not let this progress negatively affect one's dignity and social values.

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